

THE ROLE OF LATIN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICINE

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Annotation: In this article, the author examines the history, development and role of the Latin language in medicine. The article deals with issues related to the role of Latin clinical terminology in medicine, as well as in the professional career of a medical worker. The author concludes that the Latin language in medicine is, firstly, respect for history, and secondly, an indicator of the doctor's professionalism. This article may be useful to specialists in the field of linguistics and medicine.

Key words: Latsia, stages of development, Hippocrates, Aristotle, Ibn Sina, Vesalius, dead language, question.

The Latin language occupies an important place in the modern education system; it is studied both in higher educational institutions and, in a number of countries, in gymnasiums and schools. This demand for Latin is historically conditioned.

Latin belongs to the Italic branch of the Indo-European family of languages. The name "Latin" goes back to the tribe of the Latins (one of the tribes of the Apennine Peninsula), who inhabited a small region of Latium, located in the lower reaches of the Tiber River. The center of this area in the VIII century. BC e. became the city of Rome, so the inhabitants of Latium also called themselves "Romans". To the northwest of the Romans lived the highly civilized Etruscans, who had a significant impact on the culture of the nascent Roman state. Many Etruscan words entered the Latin language. To which language family the Etruscan language belongs is still unknown. Other languages of Italy, related to Latin, were gradually replaced by him. As for the Romans, having conquered in the II century BC. Ancient Greece, a country with a highly developed culture, the Romans adopted the achievements of Greek science, including medicine. Many Greek words entered the Latin language, which have survived to this day, mainly in medical names - anatomical, therapeutic, pharmacological, etc. Greek terms, while retaining their basis, were latinized and gradually gained international recognition and distribution.

This medicine was a model of the entire Roman state, it contains many names of outstanding doctors. The names of the ancient god of healing Asclepius and his daughters Hygieia and Panakia became symbols of ancient and then European medicine.

The Romans borrowed their scientific knowledge along with scientific terminology from the Greeks. When creating medical terminology in Latin, Greek words were latinized and actively replenished the vocabulary of the doctors of Rome.

The Latin language in its colloquial variety became the basis for new national languages, united under the general name of Romance. These include Italian, French, Provençal, Spanish, Portuguese, Romanian, Moldovan and others.

In the history of the Latin language, it is customary to distinguish the following stages of development:

1. Archaic period: from the first surviving written monuments, dating back to about the 7th century BC, until the beginning of the 1st century BC. The earliest samples of Latin writing are inscriptions on weapons and personal items.

2. Classical period - "golden Latin": I century BC - beginning of the 1st c. AD. During this period, the first medical schools were established in Rome.

Today, in most educational institutions, the Latin language curriculum is based on the Latin language of this particular period.

3. Postclassic period - "Silver Latin": I-II centuries AD. The most famous authors of this period are the philosopher and playwright Seneca, the satirical poets Martial and Juvenal, the most famous of the Roman historians Tacitus and Apuleius - a philosopher and writer. They clearly follow the already developed grammatical standards, but somewhat deviate from the rigid norms of the Golden Latin syntax.

4. "Late Latin": III-VI centuries AD - a qualitatively new phase in the development of the Latin language.

The formation of scientific Latin was facilitated by the development of all sciences, among which biology, medicine and veterinary medicine occupy an important place. As a result of scientific research, the Latin language is continuously enriched with new words denoting certain concepts of science, technology, production, i.e., terms.

The source of the first scientific generalizations is the ancient Greek-Latin civilization. So, Aristotle (4th century BC) made the first attempt to systematize and generalize the knowledge accumulated by mankind about the plant and animal world. Another ancient Greek scientist - Dioscorides (I century AD)

described 400 plants. Naturalist Pliny the Elder (1st century AD) collected and systematized information about the surrounding flora and fauna from the works of Greek and Roman authors.

European medicine as an independent science originated in Greece. Hippocrates, the greatest physician of antiquity, was the founder of scientific medicine. He had numerous disciples and followers who continued and developed his teachings. Naturally, the entire system of medical names was originally Greek. The Roman scientist-encyclopedist and physician Aulus Cornelius Celsus, the author of works in 8 books entitled: "On Medicine" (I century BC, first half of the 1st century AD) did a lot to develop medical terminology in Latin.). The writings of the Greek philosopher, scientist and physician Claudius Galen, who lived and worked in Rome (II century AD), are devoted to the scientific and practical issues of anatomy, etiology and treatment of various diseases, as well as the preparation of all kinds of medicines. Today, his name is associated with the so-called galenical preparations. Both Celsus and Galen paid serious attention to the improvement and refinement of the scientific language. Celsus often not only explains Greek terms, but gives the most accurate Latin equivalents.

Galen compiled a special dictionary for the writings of Hippocrates and introduced the names of a number of medicinal forms and drugs into medical terminology. Since antiquity, medical terminology began to take shape on a bilingual Greek-Latin basis. Greek-Latin bilingualism (bilingualism) is most clearly manifested in the fact that in most cases the same anatomical formations are designated in anatomical nomenclature in Latin words, and in clinical nomenclature in Greek.

In the Greek and Roman eras, veterinary medicine developed in the form of hippiatrics (the study of the treatment of horses). The most famous of the Greek hippiatricians were Apsyrtus, Pelaganius and Hierocles. Greek hippiatricians, like doctors, were guided in their activities by the teachings of Hippocrates. In the Middle Ages (VI-XIV), a significant contribution to the development of medicine was made by Arab scientists, in particular the great physician of the East, Ibn Sina (Avicenna), whose major work, The Canon of Medical Science, was translated into Latin in the 12th century. and was very popular in Western Europe. Medieval Arabic medicine and chemistry had a significant impact on European scientists. In this era, pharmaceutical terminology was replenished with Arabic words: alcohol, elixir, sirupus, etc. Much attention was paid to medicinal plants, their recognition and description.

The new flourishing and development of the natural sciences and medicine are associated with the Renaissance (XIV-XVI centuries).

A. Vesalius did a lot to improve and clarify Latin anatomical terms. A great contribution to the development of physiology was made by William Harvey, who discovered blood circulation and wrote his famous treatise *Anatomical Study of the Movement of the Heart and Blood in Animals*.

The pinnacle of the artificial classification of plants was the system developed by Carl Linnaeus. Before Linnaeus, plant species were designated by ten or more Latin words. Linnaeus introduced binominal nomenclature, according to which each species is identified by two Latin names - generic and specific.

Over a long historical period, the treatment of sick people and animals developed in a parallel way and was not professionally differentiated. With the opening of veterinary schools, faculties and institutes, the range of objects of study in the field of veterinary pathology has expanded significantly. Along with hippology, the pathology of domestic animals is studied. In the XVIII-XIX centuries, veterinary medicine is becoming an independent science. In the process of development of veterinary sciences, veterinary terminology has developed, consisting mainly of anatomical, physiological, parasitological, microbiological, virological and some technical terms that characterize the evolution, relationships and treatment of animal organisms. Along with special veterinary disciplines, general biological ones also successfully developed. Scientific schools of anatomists, physiologists, epizootologists, surgeons, therapists, pharmacologists, etc. have been created.

In the process of development of sciences, biological, medical and veterinary terminology is enriched, and there is a need to unify terms. In order to unify the terms, international congresses of scientists are periodically held.

Thanks to the Latin language, biological, medical and veterinary terminology has become international, which greatly facilitates communication between scientists around the world.

How is the Latin language related to "dead languages", but not every doctor, scientist, teacher, physicist, biologist, etc. would agree with this statement. This is due to the fact that we ourselves, without suspecting, can use words of Latin origin every day.

For example, a doctor in his work uses more than 60% of Latin terms, and a student of a medical institution of higher education, in my subjective opinion, even more.

This raises the question: "So why is the doctor obliged to know Latin terminology?" If he does not explain to patients their illnesses using Latin terminology, since not everyone knows it. It's not even considered decent or professional. But the deep knowledge of the doctor in medical terminology shows him as an expert in his craft. The ignorant will even say: "Why exactly Latin, but for example; not English, Italian, French and even Persian?" You can find out the answer in part 1. Let's go back to our original question, the answer is simple. Firstly, respect for the history of medicine, for its founders. Secondly, no matter how trite it sounds, in the documentation there must be used Latin terminology. Third, scientific work.

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